

Growth of Recognized Startups and Its Impact on Direct Employment Generation in India

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Abstract:

The startup ecosystem plays a pivotal role in driving economic growth and employment generation in India. With the government initiative of Startup India from 2016, there has been a tremendous growth in the number of recognized startups. This study focuses on the growth of number of recognized startups and its impact on job creation during the period 2016-2025. In order to analyze the secondary data which is collected from the official sources, statistical tools used are Trend analysis, Percentage analysis and Pearson correlation. The findings indicate substantial growth in the number of recognized startups and exhibits positive impact on the direct job creation.

Keywords: Startups, Employment Generation, Startup India, Economic Growth

Introduction:

Many countries in the past have benefited from its demographic dividends. Now, it is the time of India to capitalize its demographic dividend. This can happen through maximum job creation in order to absorb the growing workforce. This role of employment generation is also taken up by startups in India. In order to encourage startup ecosystem in India, schemes like Startup India have been introduced in 2016. Currently, more than 2.07 Lakh entities are recognized in India, making India the 3rd largest startup ecosystem in the India. These recognized entities by Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT) have created 21.9 lakh direct jobs.

Review of Literature:

Kamble (2025) highlights the vital role of India's startup ecosystem in generating employment and fostering economic growth. The study emphasizes that startups promote innovation and entrepreneurship, creating jobs. It also notes the positive impact of government initiatives like Startup India, which provide funding, policy support, and infrastructure to new businesses. Despite

challenges, the paper concludes that a strengthened startup ecosystem can be a boost for employment opportunities and sustainable development in India.

Dengale (2025) studies the contribution of startups to employment generation in India, focusing on their role for economic growth and innovation. The key highlights are startups create job opportunities across diverse sectors, particularly for young professionals and skilled workers. It also discusses the supportive role of government policies to uplift entrepreneurship. Despite of the challenges the faced, paper concludes that promoting a robust startup ecosystem is important for accelerating employment opportunities and India's economic development.

Kumar, Y., & Pai, K. (2020) highlights startups are generating more jobs for the jobless population in comparison of the well-established joint stock companies. It also hights that startups help in dealing with unemployment and moving towards national development, despite of numerous problems, which they face. It also suggests, that government should focus on getting rid of the hinderances for the long-term betterment in order to do business efficiently.

Yadav (2023) this study confirms that startup creates new job opportunities particularly in technology and service sector and also encourages innovation and skills. It also emphasizes regional variations and sectoral differences in job creation. The government initiatives have positive impact for building the startup ecosystem. The study concludes that startups significantly contribute immensely in order to reduce unemployment and supports sustainable economic growth in India. But as there are challenges, which requires strategic attention.

Gupta (2018) examines the impact of startups and on job creation in India by analysing employment trends within the startup ecosystem. The study also highlights the role of government initiatives such as for Startups, and regional policies in encouraging entrepreneurship and generating employment across sectors like technology, e-commerce, healthcare, and agritech. It also highlights the steady expansion of startups from metropolitan cities to Tier II and Tier III cities. The study concludes that startups significantly contribute to job creation and urges the need for continued government policy support and better data collection systems to sustain and enhance employment.

Objectives:

1. To study the growth of entities recognised as startups by DPIIT.
2. To analyse the direct job creation by recognised startups.
3. To study the relationship between the growth of startups and its impact on direct job creation.

Hypothesis:

H0 – There is a negative relationship between growth of startups and job creation.

H1 – There is a positive relationship between growth of startups and job creation.

Scope:

1. This study focuses on growth of recognized startups and its impact on employment generation in India.
2. This study is based on secondary data.
3. The tenure for this study is 2016-2025.

Research Methodology:

1. This study is combination of both of being descriptive and analytical as it tries to study the growth of recognized startups and its impact on job creation.
2. This study is based on secondary data, which has been collected from the official press release of GOI.
3. The period of the study is from 2016 to 2025.
4. The statistical tool used in this study are:
 - a. Percentage analysis
 - b. Trend analysis
 - c. Pearson Correlation
5. Independent Variable is Number of recognized startups
Depended Variable is direct employment generated by startups.

Data Analysis:

Year	Recognised Startups	Direct jobs generated
2016	502	308
2017	5473	52,055
2018	8980	1,00,968
2019	11,885	1,63,694
2020	14,852	1,81,602
2021	20,282	2,11,316
2022	26,596	2,74,920
2023	34,842	3,92,181

2024	34,294	3,51,921
2025	49,429	4,67,549

Trend analysis:

The above data of recognized startups indicates the continuous upward trend. The number of the startup from 502 in 2016 to 49,429 in 2025 shows rapid expansion.

The above data of direct jobs generated by recognized startups shows the rising trend. The number of direct jobs generated from 308 in 2016 to 4,67.549 in 2025, shows the vital role of startups in job creation. There was a slight fall in 2024, but this fall was C

Percentage analysis:

Year	Recognised Startups	Direct jobs generated
2017	990.23%	16800.97%
2018	64.07%	93.96%
2019	32.34%	62.12%
2020	24.96%	10.93%
2021	36.56%	16.36%
2022	31.13%	30.09%
2023	31.00%	42.65%
2024	-1.57%	-10.26%
2025	44.13%	32.85

At the initial year of 2017, the growth is all time high. Steady growth continued from 2018 to 2023. In 2024, there was a slight fall, but it was recovered in the following year indicating resilience.

Correlation Analysis:

The correlation coefficient of 0.989 indicates a positive correlation between no. of the recognized startups and direct job generation. This means these two variables are directly proportionate to each other. As the number of the recognized startups increases, the number of directly generated jobs also increases

Hence, H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.

Findings:

1. There has been a tremendous growth in the number of recognized startups from 2016 to 2025.
2. The direct employment generated through recognized startups has shown substantial growth.
3. The correlation coefficient of 0.989 indicates a positive relationship between no. of the recognized startups and direct job generation.

Conclusion:

The recognized startups play a significant role in creating direct job opportunities. As the number of recognized startups will increase, it will boost the job market of our country. This positive impact will help us to efficiently utilize our demographic dividend. As startups rise, expand and create more employment opportunities, it will boost the economic growth of our country. And this also fosters inclusivity.

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